

Deriving the Coupling Constants Primordial Equation From Varying Lorentzian Manifolds

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Abstract:

By using Lorentz Manifold in Euler-Lagrange equation is a mathematical framework in which fermions can arise as arbitrary variations of the manifold. Additional important result of Lorentz manifolds inside an Euler LaGrange equation is a manifestation of a mathematical Series. That series revolves around prime net variations N_p and predicts beautifully the value of the fine structure constant by the previous element in the series, i.e. the magnitude of the weak interaction.. The coupling constant equation predicts an intimate relation between bosonic fields and prime numbers, as it is primordial function. A net amount of variation on the manifold result on bosonic field propagation. The next coupling to stand at $\frac{1}{850}$ relative to the strong interaction.

Introduction

Define a Lorentz manifold:

$$\mathbf{s} = (\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{g})$$

Use it to assemble an Euler Lagrange Equation:

$$L = (s, s', t)$$
$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} - \left(\frac{d}{dt}\right) \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} = 0$$

Develop the last equation:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

If the Lorentz manifold to be stationary and no data is attainable from the first three terms, we can require the manifold to those two conditions

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad -\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

If these two are hold to be true, we have areas of extremum curvature on the manifold and negative time invariant acceleration. The demand of extrunum curvature to stay as they are overtime means the acceleration cannot affect them – if so, directed away from them. This in agreement with what we speculate as "dark energy".

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial \delta g'}{\partial \partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (0.13)$$

δg As amount of arbitrary variations, which by demands of stationarity we require to vanish:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \delta g$$

$$\delta g = 0$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 > 0$$

$$\delta g_3 + \delta g_4 < 0$$

If

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 + \delta g_4 \neq 0$$

Than the overall series cannot vanish, by that logic we need equal amounts of plus and minuses. The overall amount must be even and summed as zero. Suppose that we had three distinct elements, two pluses and minus:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 > 0$$

or

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 < 0$$

Demanding the series to vanish this will defy the result, and so there could not be three distinct elements in the series, else the overall series will not vanish. As a result of those sceneries, we require the series to have an even amount of variation elements, manifesting as two distinct elements in the series, which differ in sign.

If we allow those sub elements in the series to vary as well, and by the above reasoning, there are only two elements in the series, they are varying in a discrete way, or forming a group. Let it be only four elements in the series and one of the pluses just changed its nature

$$\mathbf{O}: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 \neq 0$$

There must be a way to bring it back to where it was, so the overall series can vanish, it takes another map, on the varying element to bring it back to where it was.

$$\mathbf{Y}: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1$$

Therefore, to bring an element to itself given only two varying elements in the series we need two distinct maps, which attach a varying element to itself, by a threefold combination. $\delta g_1(O)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1$ For example. Even though the sub elements in the series are varying, the overall series can vanish.

Now, count all the ways of possible combinations of those elements. We are going to analyze by the integral signs. Since it is a group, there is a natural map, which change an element to itself. One built his analysis firstly on those natural maps.

So:

(1(e)1(e)1)

2(e)2(e)2

(221)

(112)

(211)

(122)

(212)

(121)

The first two combinations are by the natural maps and one used them to build the other combinations. Overall, there are eight such combinations and additional one arrow combination, which yield (333). Here is how one built it, starting from those two natural maps. (Arrows to variations, colors to pairings):

Therefore, we have Lorenzian manifold with arbitrary variations, which vanish into matter based on that idea. One does not know whether these are the actual variations, as the mathematics does not entail any details about that. Therefore, the graph could be inaccurate in elements order. The colors meant to elements pairing.

Reader does not have to agree with what one did, but as one will calculate the ratios of all the forces known, one kindly asks the reader to keep reading as some truth seem to obey the reasoning one is suggesting.

Deriving the Coupling Constant Equation

Theorem (1) – nature will not allow a prime amount of variation to appear by itself. Define prime to be $(2n+1)$ variations.

1.1) Prime amounts appear in pairs.

Theorem (2): Nature will generate force if a **prime net amount of arbitrary variation will appear**. Net variations will appear when combine two amounts of prime variations.

Two does not appear, as it is an even amount of variations, which vanish.

Define N_V as the series of prime net variations and the number one.

$$N_V = 2V + 1 \quad V \geq 0$$

Count all the prime pairs of variations,

(3,3) (3,5) (3,7) (3,11), (3,13) ...
 (5,3) (5,5) (5,7) (5,11) (5,13) ...
 (7,3) (7,5) (7,7) (7,11) (7,13) ...
 ...
 (29,19)(29,23), (29,29), (29,31) ...

That is a tedious work, but here is the great part. **We only need to do it twice** to find what nature does repeatedly.

Since we have only two varying elements in the series, we can eliminate almost all the options, as we require obtaining **a sum that is divisible by two and after yields a number divisible by three**. By The following reasoning:

Two as we have only two varying elements. Three as these elements create a certain amount of threefold combinations. The sums satisfying the condition are

(5,13) or (7,11) and (29,31).

Of course, there are more as N_V has no limit, but as one mentioned, it took two pairs to understand the principle:

Theorem (3) –Each prime pair should have a net variation element N_V proportional to Total Variations value divided by two. This will be vivid with actual examples:

Analyze the (7, 11) Total variations pair with $N_V = (+1)$:

Total variations sum is divisible by two:

$$18/2 = 9$$

And then by three

$$9/3 = 3$$

We know that we have $N_V = (+1)$ so it can be extracted to yield:

$$F(1) = 8 + 1$$

However, even amounts of variations vanish so we can ignore the element 8 and write:

$$F_1 = 1$$

Analyze the next pair of Total Variation (29, 31) with $N_V = (+3)$

$$29 + 31 = 60$$

$$60/2 = 30$$

In addition, three divisible. We know we have three net variations so extract:

$$27 + 3$$

Now that is all you need to complete the series and calculate the **next element**:

Notice:

$$27 = 24 + (3)$$

$$(8 * 3) = 24$$

Obtain the ratio:

$$[8 + 1]: [27 + 3] = [8 + 1]: [24 + (3)] + 3$$

$$[8 + 1]: [27 + 3] = [8 + 1]: [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3$$

Next element $V = 2$ and $N_V = +5$ **so if the overall idea to be correct** we take this element, multiply by the even sum of the previous element in the series, **add extra invariant (3)**, and we know we need add to the sum the extracted N_V .

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 = 128.$$

Next in line:

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 = 850$$

$$[(840 * 11) + (3)] + 11 = 9254$$

Nature is than the **Interplay between total arbitrary variations to net variations**. To calculate the magnitude of an element R:

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{0}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{2}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

Overview of reasoning:

Axiom – prime amount of arbitrary variations pair to each other

Their overall sum must be dividable by two and three

Two distinct elements, which create threefold combinations

Define generated force as prime net variation in which we associate N_V elementt

$\frac{\text{total variations}}{2} \propto$ to N_V element by the relative size of total pairing

Net variation function cannot contain an even, as it will vanish

We searched for the first two prime pairs and derived $8 + (1)$ and $27 + (3)$

We saw that nature multiply the even sum by the next element of N_V

We found the invariant (3) element.

We obtained a number to which we add the extracted net variation

We calculated the next element to be exactly 128 and the two next interactions:

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ...$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

One would like to elaborate on the three critical theorems made, as they are vital for the unification between general relativity and quantum theory. This is the purpose of this last part.

"Theorem (1) – nature will not allow a prime amount of variation to appear by itself. Define prime to be $(2n+1)$ variations.

1.1) Prime amounts appear in pairs."

Theorem (1) - The physical meaning of that theorem is that bosonic fields cannot be propagated from nowhere. The 8T correlate bosonic propagation to prime net variations of the manifold, and bosons, as we know them, propagate from fermions, which vanish in even number of variations.

Theorem (1.1) – even amount of variations is the result of two prime numbers combined. So to create variation cluster vanishing into matter we need two primes to appear in a pair.

"Theorem (2): Nature will generate force if a **prime net amount of arbitrary variation will appear**. Net variations will appear when combine two amounts of prime variations.

Two does not appear, as it is an even amount of variations, which vanish."

Theorem (2): In continuation of theorem (1), after variation cluster vanished into matter, two distinct elements in threefold combination, a net variation, which is prime can propagate from within it. The feature of the bosonic propagation is their prime number amount of variations, and therefore their expansion across the entire matrix. A boson must propagate from an even amount of variations, which is matter.

Theorem (3): "Each prime pair should have a net variation element N_V proportional to Total Variations value divided by two"

Theorem (3): Each net variation is proportional to the average of the elements in the pair. There could not be net variation $N_V = +(101)$ propagating from (7,11) total variation pair. It does not make sense.

The three theorems in be put in concise and simple manner:

- (1) Bosonic fields cannot propagate from nowhere
- (2) Bosonic Fields propagate from matter clusters
- (3) Bosonic fields are infinite in kind and isomorphic to prime numbers or one.

Theorem (3) was the critical theorem that eventually allowed calculating the value of the fine structure constant and validating the entire framework.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)